

THE IMPACT OF PERCEIVED SOCIAL SELF-EFFICACY ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF UNITAR INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY'S STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The research investigates the connection between academic achievement among students in UNITAR International University and their perceived social self-efficacy. Their future success is largely dependent on their academic performance, as determined by their CGPA. Meanwhile, students' self-confidence in their capacity to control social interactions is known as perceived social self-efficacy, and it may have an impact on their academic performance. This study aimed to ascertain whether or not students with a higher perceived level of social self-efficacy perform better academically. A cross-sectional, non-experimental, quantitative correlational design was employed. An online survey was used to gather information from 371 convenience-sampled students. The PSSES by Smith and Betz (2000) gauge students' social confidence, and CGPA was used to gauge academic achievement. The results indicated a moderately positive but statistically significant relationship between academic achievement and perceived social self-efficacy. Higher PSSE scores linked to better academic performance likely stem from more peer discussions, group projects, and help-seeking behavior. However, academic success also depends on other factors like time management, emotional health, and learning methods. This study helps us better understand how social confidence impacts students' overall achievement and emphasizes the need to support students' social skills along with their academic growth.

Keywords: Perceived Social Self-Efficacy, Academic Performance, CGPA, University Students, Social Confidence

INTRODUCTION

The academic success is vital for the future employment prospects and growth of the learners. Thus, universities try to understand which psychological elements contribute to the students' success, and one such element identified by many scholars was the self-efficacy. Bandura (1997) said that the individual's belief in their capacity to organise and accomplish the actions required to manage prospective situations is referred to as self-efficacy. Derived from Social Cognitive Theory, self-efficacy affects motivation and persistence (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2020; Bandura, 1997). In relation to academia, the existing literature is more interested in academic self-efficacy, defined as a measure of students' belief in their abilities to undertake academic activities such as studying, assignment completion, and getting high grades (Pajares, 1996). However, social self-efficacy refers to one's confidence in being able to perform effectively in social encounters involving communication, teamwork, and asking for help (Smith & Betz, 2000). Both constructs belong to the category of self-efficacy, but there are conceptual differences between them: academic self-

efficacy focuses on specific tasks, while social self-efficacy is about interpersonal skills (Bandura, 1997; Smith & Betz, 2000). This model indicates that social self-efficacy reflects an individual's perception of his or her social skills, which affects academic performance as a result of the interaction between academic and social functions that university students have to handle simultaneously. This aspect becomes especially relevant for the context of higher education institutions, since nowadays there is a growing trend towards making learning more social in nature, including discussions and collaborations (Tinto, 1997; Zajacova et al., 2005). Students who perceive themselves as socially competent will participate in classroom discussions and group projects and help-seeking behaviour which essential for their academic success because these activities promote collaborative learning and improved academic performance, whereas students with lower social self-efficacy may avoid social interactions, experience academic stress, and struggle to seek support, negatively impacting achievement. These behavioural differences suggest that social self-efficacy may influence academic performance indirectly through engagement and participation mechanisms (Bandura, 1997; Zajacova et al., 2005). Previous studies support this relationship: Atoum and Al-Momani (2018) found that higher perceived self-efficacy was linked to better performance among secondary school pupils. Shahed et al. (2016) reported that students who have better perceived social support and self-efficacy achieved superior academic outcomes.

Although self-efficacy has been extensively researched in relation to its impact on academic performance, little attention has been given to perceived social self-efficacy among Malaysian university students. Existing Malaysian studies have largely concentrated on academic self-efficacy, with limited analytical attention given to perceived social self-efficacy as a distinct construct (Othman & Leng, 2011; Zajacova et al., 2005). This lack of differentiation limits understanding of how social interaction confidence uniquely contributes to academic outcomes. Learners in the university domain are not only required to perform academic tasks but are also required to engage in socially embedded academic activities. Students who possess low perceived social self-efficacy may face difficulties in performing these social activities, which may, in turn, affect their academic performance. Furthermore, there is insufficient empirical evidence examining this relationship within Malaysian private universities, where diverse student populations and collaborative learning environments may increase the importance of social competence (Ministry of Higher Education Malaysia, 2020; Othman & Leng, 2011). Although literature indicates that social confidence contributes to students' engagement, the link between perceived social self-efficacy with performance of academic, as measured by CGPA, has yet to be fully researched in private universities in Malaysia. Therefore, this study addresses this gap by providing a clearer theoretical and contextual examination of perceived social self-efficacy in relation to academic performance within a Malaysian private higher education setting.

The study aims to investigate the performance of academic among UNITAR International University students based on their CGPA, and to explore the outcome of perceived social self-efficacy on performance of academic. Specifically, the study examines the relationship between perceived social self-efficacy and academic performance rather than treating CGPA as a determinant of performance. For this study, perceived social self-efficacy is determined as students' confidence in managing social interactions and maintaining interpersonal relationships, operationally measured using the PSSES (Smith & Betz, 2000). Academic performance refers to students' overall achievement, operationally measured via CGPA. UNITAR International University students are individuals actively enrolled in undergraduate or postgraduate programmes at UNITAR during data collection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Social Cognitive Theory by Albert Bandura explains that people can function in daily lives due to the communication between behavior, individual attributes, and situational factors (Bandura, 1986). Within Bandura's theory, self-efficacy is identified as a central motivational construct influencing learning behaviours and academic achievement (Graham & Weiner, 1996; Zimmerman, 2000). Nevertheless, self-efficacy is a multidimensional concept because it differs in various areas. Social self-efficacy is the belief that one can cope with social situations and maintain social relations effectively, especially those related to academia (Smith & Betz, 2000). It is crucial to understand that social self-efficacy is very important in the field of education since it involves cooperation, peer learning, and communication skills. Those students who demonstrate high levels of social self-efficacy will be more active participants in class discussions, group work, and asking for help when necessary.

The empirical evidence shows that social efficacy behavior is directly related to high levels of engagement and achievement at school. For example, students exhibiting high levels of self-confidence in social situations exhibit higher levels of participation in class discussion and activities. This results in better academic performance (Shahed et al., 2016; Atoum & Al-Momani, 2018).

Nevertheless, students who lack a sense of social self-efficacy are more likely to be exposed to academic pressure, engage less in classroom interactions, and exhibit poor academic commitment, potentially compromising their academic performance (Wong et al., 2020). Moreover, the significance of self-efficacy in academic success is widely acknowledged within higher education literature. Higher levels of academic self-efficacy lead to superior academic outcomes primarily because of enhanced motivation and perseverance (Alzabidi et al., 2024). Likewise, Aziz et al. (2020) established a correlation between emotional intelligence and self-efficacy amongst university students.

Nonetheless, it should be noted that the current research still predominantly focuses on general and academic self-efficacy while paying insufficient attention to the significance of perceived social self-efficacy as an individual variable affecting academic performance. Also, even though the body of knowledge related to academic achievement in colleges is not lacking at all, the specific effects of social self-efficacy on academic outcomes in a private Malaysian university setting have not yet been investigated extensively.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

A non-experimental correlational research design was adopted in the current study to examine the correlation between the variables under investigation (i.e., social self-efficacy and academic achievement). The use of a correlational research design is deemed proper since it allowed the researcher to detect correlations among the variables under investigation without altering them (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Field, 2018). Cross-sectional research design was used, where data were collected only once. It is due to the fact that it allowed the researcher to collect relevant information quickly (Bryman, 2016). The study also used a between-subjects experimental design in which every participant only provided one set of data to avoid response biases (Gravetter & Forzano, 2018). Given that the study aims to

examine relationships rather than establish causality, a correlational design is methodologically appropriate.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopted the Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986), a theory that emphasizes the importance of cognitive beliefs in influencing behavior. In this theory, social self-efficacy refers to how confident students feel about handling social relationships, interacting in the learning environment, and asking for help where needed. Perceived social self-efficacy will be considered the independent variable, while academic performance, measured by CGPA, will be the dependent variable. It can be assumed that perceived social self-efficacy contributes positively to academic success.

Figure 1. Diagram of Conceptual Framework

SAMPLE

A total of 371 university students from UNITAR International University were involved in the research. They were enrolled and participated voluntarily in the study. Convenience sampling was applied by the researcher to conduct research effectively within the allocated time and resources. The respondents were both men and women and comprised students from different faculties and levels. However, convenience sampling introduces selection bias and lowers the external validity of the findings due to the representation of a wide variety of academic background and experiences among students (Etikan et al., 2016). Despite this limitation, the sample size is considered adequate for correlational analysis, as larger samples increase statistical power and improve estimate stability (Field, 2018). The demographics, such as gender, age, and educational attainment, were included to offer further insight into the characteristics of the respondents for descriptive analysis.

INSTRUMENT

The Perceived Social Self-Efficacy Scale (PSSSES) by Smith & Betz (2000) was utilized in the current research to gauge the extent of one's self-confidence when engaging in

social activities and building social connections. The scale is created according to Bandura's self-efficacy theory, which asserts the behavior and outcomes of individuals are determined by their beliefs in their capacity to successfully execute a task in different situations.

The PSSES scale is a scale that has 25 questions for measuring the extent of confidence of individuals within different social situations. These questions are rated using a five-point Likert scale where respondents would be rated from 1 which stands for 'not at all confident' to 5 which means 'totally confident'. Respondents are rated with 2 when they are somewhat confident; 3 when they are neither confident nor not confident, and 4 when they are very confident. This scale assesses various domains including initiation of conversation, maintaining relationships, conflict resolution among friends as well as public speaking. The reliability coefficients for this scale in previous researches include Cronbach's alpha of 0.94 for the PSSES according to Smith & Betz (2000). In this research, reliability is estimated by using Cronbach's alpha. The PSSES scale showed a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.956$ for 25 items, indicating excellent internal consistency (Taber, 2018).

DATA ANALYSIS

Various statistical analyses were carried out. First, to examine whether the CGPA will determine the performance of academic among students of UNITAR International University (H1: The CGPA of UNITAR students determines their academic performance), the CGPA was analyzed directly as an indicator of academic performance. The study calculated the mean and standard deviation values for its descriptive statistical analysis. The mean value of CGPA was used to represent the academic performance of students.

Second, to examine whether perceived social self-efficacy influences academic performance (H2: There is a positive relationship between students' perceived social self-efficacy and academic performance), Spearman rho's correlation analysis was carried out. The correlation analysis examined the strength and nature of the association between CGPA and PSSES. The PSSES is used to measure students' social confidence levels.

Spearman's correlation was selected instead of Pearson's correlation as the data did not meet the assumptions of normality and, or, or involved ordinal-level Likert scale measurements, making it a more appropriate non-parametric alternative (Field, 2018). A high score of PSSES represents students' perceived social self-efficacy; that is, students' beliefs about their capabilities to interact with others. A positive correlation indicates that high perceived social self-efficacy among students will achieve high academic performance.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

This research was done in accordance with established ethical norms (American Psychological Association, 2017). Voluntary participation and obtaining of informed consent prior to collecting the data were ensured. The participants were thoroughly informed about the nature of the research and its aims as well as the right to leave the experiment at any moment without negative consequences. The aspect of confidentiality and anonymity was strictly maintained since there was no collection of any personal data of participants. They were allowed to proceed with the questionnaire at their own pace without any external influence. Data were only used for research purposes and safely disposed of within a year.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

The respondents' demographic details provide the study with crucial context and ensure that the results can be interpreted according to the of the participants' backgrounds.

Table 1. Frequency Table of Age

Age Range	Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
18-20	90	24.3	24.3	24.3
21-23	155	41.8	41.8	66.0
24-26	110	29.6	29.6	95.7
27 and above	16	4.3	4.3	100.0
Total	371	100.0	100.0	

The majority of participants are in the age range of 21 -23 years old, which accounts for 41.8%. This group of respondents may typically fall under the undergraduate groups of students. The minority respondents fall under those with above 27 years old. These respondents may either fall under the category of postgraduate students or the undergraduate students who started their education journey later.

Table 2. Frequency Table of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Male	174	46.9	46.9	46.9
Female	197	53.1	53.1	100.0
Total	371	100.0	100.0	

Gender representation in the study highlights whether the sample is balanced or skewed towards a particular group. The survey was answered by the majority of the female group, with 53.1%, whereas the male students represent the remaining 46.9%. Despite the difference, the survey has been fairly balanced between both genders.

Table 3. Frequency Table of Semester

Semester	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
1	17	4.6	4.6	4.6

2	51	13.7	13.7	18.3
3	43	11.6	11.6	29.9
4	72	19.4	19.4	49.3
5	69	18.6	18.6	67.9
6	57	15.4	15.4	83.3
7	47	12.7	12.7	96.0
8	11	3.0	3.0	98.9
9	2	0.5	0.5	99.5
10	2	0.5	0.5	100.0
Total	371	100.0	100.0	

From the table, it is clear that the biggest group of respondents are currently in their fourth semester with 19.4% representing them. Meanwhile, the respondents are fewer from the last two semesters, which hold 0.5% respectively.

PRELIMINARY DATA ANALYSIS/SCREENING/CLEANING

The Academic Performance section has a total of 17 missing values. The CGPA was not provided by 17 respondents. This is perhaps because these students are still in their first semester and have not taken any significant examinations yet, so at the time of data collection, their CGPA was not recorded. However, they were included in the survey overall and provided insightful answers to other sections, especially when it came to evaluating Perceived Social Self-Efficacy (PSSE), even though they were unable to participate in the analysis about academic performance. As a result, their data remained valuable for analyses like group comparisons and descriptive statistics. There are still 354 valid cases for statistical analysis in spite of the missing value.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Academic Performance

The academic performance among UNITAR students is examined through their CGPA. The following table shows the descriptive statistics of the UNITAR students' CGPA.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Respondents' CGPA

N	354
Standard Deviation	0.68240
Minimum CGPA	1.10
Maximum CGPA	4.00

As mentioned in preliminary data analysis, due to 17 missing values, the valid response for CGPA is 354. The table displays the respondents with the lowest CGPA is 1.10, which falls under the category of fail. On the other hand, the highest CGPA of the respondents is 4.00, which indicates distinction.

Perceived Social Self-Efficacy

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Respondents' PSSE

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Start a conversation with someone you don't know very well.	2.86	1.100
Express your opinion to a group of people discussing a subject that is of interest to you.	3.19	1.164
Work on a school, work, community or other project with people you don't know very well.	3.07	1.120
Help to make someone you've recently met feel comfortable with your group of friends.	3.33	1.176
Share with a group of people an interesting experience you once had.	3.27	1.158
Put yourself in a new and different social situation.	3.09	1.147
Volunteer to help organise an event.	3.23	1.211
Ask a group of people who are planning to engage in a social activity (e.g., go to a movie) if you can join them.	2.96	1.224
Get invited to a party that is being given by a prominent or popular individual.	3.00	1.182
Volunteer to help lead a group or organisation.	3.24	1.238

Keep your side of the conversation.	3.26	1.121
Be involved in group activities.	3.48	1.172
Find someone to spend a weekend afternoon with.	3.25	1.213
Express your feelings to another person.	3.13	1.218
Find someone to go to lunch with.	3.27	1.180
Ask someone out on a date.	2.89	1.277
Go to a party or social function where you probably won't know anyone.	2.85	1.241
Ask someone for help when you need it.	3.21	1.205
Make friends with a member of your peer group.	3.36	1.145
Join a lunch or dinner table where people are already sitting and talking.	3.08	1.225
Make friends in a group where everyone else knows each other.	3.18	1.210
Ask someone out after s/he was busy the first time you asked.	3.11	1.234
Get a date to a dance that your friends are going to.	3.03	1.309
Call someone you've met and would like to know better.	3.22	1.230
Ask a potential friend out for coffee.	3.41	1.210

The table above shows descriptive statistics of respondents' PSSE. The highest mean score was by item "Be involved in group activities" ($m=3.48$, $SD=1.172$), while the lowest score was by item "Go to a party or social function where you probably won't know anyone" ($m=2.85$, $SD=1.241$).

Correlation between CGPA & Perceived Social Self-Efficacy

Table 6. Correlation between Respondent's CGPA and PSSE

Variable	CGPA
Perceived Social Self-Efficacy	.262**

Based on Table 6, there is a modest to moderately positive correlation between these two variables, as indicated by the Spearman's correlation coefficient ($r=0.262$).

The first hypothesis (H1) holds that the CGPA reflects students' academic performance. As CGPA is a generally accepted and standardised indication of academic accomplishment in higher education, this assumption is operationally supported rather than experimentally evaluated in this work. Therefore, H1 is accepted on a conceptual basis.

The second research hypothesis (H2) asserts that there is a positive relationship between perceived social self-efficacy and academic achievement. The correlation between perceived social self-efficacy and CGPA scores is fairly positive ($r = 0.262$, $p < .001$). This supports the assertion that students who have high social confidence levels tend to engage in educational conversations, collaborative learning, and seek help, all of which lead to academic success. Thus, H2 is accepted.

The third hypothesis (H3) argues that students who have better perceived social self-efficacy have considerably higher CGPAs than those with lower levels. Although a significant association was found, the moderate strength of the correlation ($r = 0.262$) suggests that perceived social self-efficacy is not a strong independent predictor of academic achievement. This suggests that, in addition to social confidence, numerous interconnected factors influence academic accomplishment.

These additional factors may include time management abilities, which influence students' ability to efficiently balance academic burden and deadlines. Stress and anxiety can have a major impact on focus, motivation, and overall academic performance. In addition, academic engagement such as attending lectures, having constant study habits, and participating in learning exercises are important factors when measuring performance outcomes. Some other possible independent variables include learning approaches, self-regulation skills, and availability of academic and social resources.

Thus, while perceived social self-efficacy improves academic achievement by increasing involvement and interaction, it works in tandem with other cognitive, emotional, and behavioural aspects. Consequently, H3 is rejected.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study were interpreted in relation to existing literature to determine whether they confirm or extend previous research on academic performance and self-efficacy.

Because the descriptive analysis of the range, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation reflected the academic distribution of the sample and was consistent with institutional practice, the results, with regard to the first research question, support the idea that CGPA is still a dependable and effective indicator of UNITAR students' academic achievement. This supports the validity of CGPA or GPA as an outcome variable in Malaysian educational research, as it was also used to measure academic achievement by Alzabidi et al. (2024) and Aziz et al. (2020). Thus, the idea that CGPA is a good indicator of academic achievement is upheld based on accepted research standards and academic practice. This demonstrates that the CGPA remains the most widely accepted proxy for academic success in Malaysian higher education environments, particularly in outcome-based assessment systems that necessitate performance measurement standards.

As for the second research question, it should be stated that there is a positive correlation between PSSE and CGPA (Spearman's rho ($r = 0.262$, $p < .001$)). The result means that students who have high social self-efficacy are successful in their studies. The mentioned results coincide with the findings of Atoum and Al-Momani (2018), who reported that perceived self-efficacy is positively correlated with the level of academic achievement, as well as with those of Shahed et al. (2016), who found out that self-efficacy had a positive correlation with academic performance in visually impaired students. In addition, according to Wong et al. (2020), it is possible to claim that peer support and motivation increase perceived self-efficacy, and, based on the findings of Aziz et al. (2020), it is possible to state that there is a positive correlation between self-efficacy and academic performance. By specifically focusing on social self-efficacy, which is often overlooked in local research, the present study extends prior findings and validates the hypothesis that students' academic success is positively associated with their perceived social self-efficacy. This relationship is also explained by behavioural mechanisms, which show that students with higher PSSE are more likely to seek assistance, actively participate in discussions in the classroom, and collaborate effectively in group learning activities, all of which contribute to improved academic understanding and performance.

In answering the third research question, although a moderately strong and significant relationship between PSSE and CGPA was found, it was also noted that students with lower CGPA but higher PSSE indicate that academic performance is not entirely a function of social self-efficacy. According to the Social Cognitive Theory, as articulated by Bandura (1997), self-efficacy undoubtedly makes a significant contribution to behavior and performance. However, it seems that the connection between the two is more complicated than initially thought. For instance, Robbins et al. (2004) suggested that time management skills, intrinsic motivation, psychological well-being, and support systems affect academic performance. This idea was corroborated by Britton and Tesser (1991), who correlated time management skills with academic success, Eisenberg et al. (2007), who highlighted the importance of mental health problems as obstacles to learning, and Malecki and Demaray (2006), who proved that social support could serve as a mediator of academic pressure. Consequently, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis has no evidence backing it up, since, while PSSE is a favorable factor, it is certainly not the only one that determines CGPA. Furthermore, this implies that academic accomplishment should be viewed as a multidimensional construct influenced by cognitive,

emotional, behavioural, and contextual elements rather than a single psychological trait.

In general, the results obtained from the study not only confirm previous findings but also go beyond what is already known regarding the influence of social self-efficacy on academic achievement. It can be stated that social self-efficacy has an important role to play in the process of learning, but it cannot be considered the only variable affecting this process in Malaysian universities. This emphasises the necessity of creating integrated student support techniques that improve interpersonal competence, academic skills, and psychological well-being in higher education institutions.

The implications of the findings of the study can be far-reaching for students, educators, and institutions of learning. Understanding the significance of social self-efficacy can, for instance, help students develop themselves in terms of social skills such as asking questions, engaging in discussions, and study groups, which can help them academically. Similarly, for the educator, the findings of the study highlight the need to develop a socially supportive classroom environment where students can express themselves socially. This can be done by incorporating activities such as study groups, presentations, and guidance, where students can develop themselves socially, thereby gaining more confidence academically. From the perspective of the institution, the implications of the study can be far-reaching for institutions such as UNITAR, among others, by conducting training workshops for students in interpersonal communication, leadership skills, and self-determination, not only to develop a supportive learning environment but also to empower students who lack self-confidence. Moreover, given the importance of collaborative learning and student engagement in the Malaysian context, the emotional and social development aspects of learning can be crucial to the formulation of an overall education plan. These interventions may be particularly effective when embedded into co-curricular programmes, peer mentoring systems, and structured group-based learning initiatives, which can systematically enhance students' social confidence and academic engagement over time.

This study employed a cross-sectional design, which data were collected at one specific time. While this method is useful for identifying relationships between variables, it can't determine cause and effect. For example, while we discovered that students with higher PSSE have higher CGPAs, we cannot say definitively whether social self-efficacy led to higher academic performance or whether academic success increased students' confidence in social situations. As a result, additional research using longitudinal or experimental designs would be useful in determining the direction of this link and giving stronger causal evidence.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings and limitations, future researchers should consider conducting a longitudinal study, in which the same group of students is tracked over a longer period of time, would be an effective approach. This could help researchers better understand how students' social self-efficacy changes throughout their university careers, and how those changes may affect their academic performance in the long run. Future research also can examine other variables that may influence or affect PSSE, such as emotional intelligence, drive, level of stress, social support systems, and even cultural factors. These aspects may help explain why some students perform better academically in spite of having lower PSSE, or conversely. Including these variables may provide a more comprehensive picture of what influences student performance. With the objective to provide more in-depth

qualitative insights into how students understand and use social self-efficacy in academic settings, future research may also benefit from employing mixed-method techniques like focus groups or interviews.

In conclusion, it can be stated that there is a moderate and statistically significant correlation between PSSE and academic performance among UNITAR International University students. Therefore, it can be stated that while PSSE does not entirely influence academic performance, it has a significant influence, especially when it comes to situations where communication with other people, cooperation with other people, and help-seeking behaviors are crucial. Students with high PSSE are more likely to form helpful peer relationships, communicate efficiently with lecturers, cooperate with other members, and seek academic help whenever they need it. While these behaviors are not directly measurable with academic performance, they are crucial for academic success in today's academic environment that emphasizes cooperation, communication, and interaction. Through the process of enhanced academic engagement and adaptive learning practices, these behavioural mechanisms offer a potential explanation for the observed association, indicating that PSSE indirectly supports academic achievement.

This study has revealed that it might be misleading for any academic institution to rely on PSSES as a basis for predicting academic success because of its low correlation. Academic institutions should be very careful while designing academic interventions that only aim to enhance academic characteristics that are measured by these scores, such as PSSE. Academic institutions should take into account the overall academic environment while designing such academic interventions. To more successfully increase student achievement, interventions should take a comprehensive approach that combines the development of social self-efficacy with academic skill training, emotional support networks, and learning method refinement.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Author confirms that there is no conflict of interest present in this study.

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